

Impact of Experiential Marketing on Customer Satisfaction with Reference to Restaurant Sector in Sri Lanka; A Study on Pizza Hut

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ABSTRACT

Ever-changing client requirements need invaluable and lasting impressions to retain loyal consumers and acquire new client bases. Experiential Marketing, in fact, is a tool used to attract consumers into interactive brand experiences. Although experiential marketing boosts the restaurant industry, the use of experiential marketing has not been thoroughly documented in prior studies, and a limited number of studies have been undertaken in culturally diversified Sri Lanka, yet no research study has been conducted for well-established brands like Pizza Hut. The goal of this study is to address that empirical and contextual gap by investigating the influence of experiential marketing on customer satisfaction in the Sri Lankan restaurant industry focusing on Pizza Hut. Five experiential marketing aspects; sense, feel, think, act, and relate have been utilised by researchers to analyse the consumer

experience. Strategic Experiential Modules (SEM), first presented by Schmitt are the source of sense, feel, think, act, and relate and the module was not altered. The study employs a deductive approach and using the convenience sampling method, 305 respondents were selected from the population to participate in the survey. Data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire with 5-point Likert scales, and hypotheses were evaluated using a regression model in SPSS. Overall, the study's findings suggest that experiential marketing significantly impacts customer satisfaction, thus confirming the objectives of the research study. Managers in the hospitality and restaurant industry can utilise the findings of this study to gain valuable customer insights and develop effective marketing strategies.

Keywords - **Experiential Marketing, Customer Satisfaction, Restaurant Industry**

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction and Problem Identification

Experiential marketing represents the evolution and strategic integration of various established marketing approaches - sense, feel, think, act, and relate marketing (Jinyong, 2003). It has recently gained prominence as a marketing strategy due to its capacity to enable organisations to create a synergistic effect through the systematic integration of these elements, frequently resulting in favourable business outcomes (Jinyong, 2003). Experiential marketing has become an increasingly fundamental strategy for differentiation among consumer brands in competitive industries (Schmitt, 2010). While experiential marketing techniques requiring customer participation may differ in emphasis and methodology across industries, the core philosophy can be applied universally whether in education, hospitality and restaurant, manufacturing or information technology (Jinyong, 2003). The culinary industry was chosen for the discussion of the concept as it has the opportunity and capacity to expand since both food and drinks are the fundamental necessities for humankind, which will always find the chance to evolve through time and cuisines (Yanti Febrini et al., 2019).

Regarding the restaurant sector in Sri Lanka, the industry has been rapidly growing, being one of the best tourist destinations in the world, making the country and industry an Eden for studies (Sri Lanka Tourism Development Authority, 2023). In addition, more and more local restaurants and chains

have emerged, and global restaurant chains have entered the Sri Lankan market (Nirmani et al., 2017). Currently, Sri Lanka is not only home for local restaurant brands but also for multinational brands like Pizza Hut, KFC, McDonalds' and Domino's Pizza (Patabandige & Yapa, 2016).

Since its founding in 1958, Pizza Hut has grown to be a well-known brand in the restaurant sector, with more than 18,000 locations currently operating in 116 countries (Mendis et al., 2022). Pizza Hut launched its first restaurant in Sri Lanka in 1993 as the first multinational restaurant brand to enter the Sri Lankan market and has expanded since to over a hundred locations across the island, which makes Pizza Hut more reachable and affordable by all Sri Lankans while receiving the same taste throughout the island (Devendra, 2023). Pizza Hut stands out from other eateries in terms of accessibility, affordability, and uniqueness, prompting the researcher to explore how experiential marketing influences customer satisfaction (Udurawana, 2014).

Restaurants are not only the places where customers tend to satisfy one of the basic needs of humans, hunger, but also the places where consumers experience excitement, gratification, satisfaction and peace of mind, which not every customer feels when consuming foods and beverages from a restaurant (Ha & Jang, 2010). A unique experience that restaurants give to their customers is an important strategy to give customers memorable dining while retaining customers (Jang et al., 2011). This experiential method emphasises developing holistic experiences that appeal to

consumers' senses, emotions, minds, and interpersonal connections in addition to their utilitarian product features (Smilansky, 2017). Furthermore, research shows experiential marketing can positively influence consumer perceptions, satisfaction, and loyalty (Bilgihan, 2016; C. H. J. Wu & Liang, 2009).

According to Tam & Tai (2014), the majority of research on the impact of experiential marketing, however, has been done in Western countries and industrialised countries. Understanding the effects of experiential marketing on customers in developing nations such as Sri Lanka other than Western ones is inadequate (Tam & Tai, 2014). This is a challenge for firms operating in a variety of international marketplaces because research from Western contexts may not be universally applicable (Amin & Tarun, 2019). Furthermore, the use of experiential marketing in the hospitality and tourism industry, which also consists of the restaurant industry, is scarce in literature even when experience is considered a significant benefit for these industries (Pham & Huang, 2015; Williams, 2006).

On the academic front, most prior research has focused solely on other countries and industries, resulting in a considerable knowledge gap regarding how consumers in the Sri Lankan restaurant industry respond to experiential strategies, and the study makes a substantial effort to address the shortage of empirical data on the efficiency of experiential marketing in the island nation, Sri Lanka and Sri Lankan restaurants (Tam & Tai, 2014). Moreover, not only a knowledge gap but also there is a significant

gap in the literature in the hospitality and tourism sector, including eateries (Amin & Tarun, 2019; Pham & Huang, 2015; Williams, 2006). The influence of experiential marketing has been broadly discussed in the literature with customer repurchase intention, brand equity building, customer revisit intention and customer loyalty, but the impact of experiential marketing on customer satisfaction is rarely discussed, indicating a significant gap in the literature (Ellitan, 2022; Mukiira et al., 2017; Salomão & Santos, 2022; Sehani & Hettiarachchy, 2022).

The restaurant industry has traditionally relied on conventional marketing, but experiential marketing offers unique potential (Amin & Tarun, 2019). From an applied standpoint, the study provides significant insights that enable Sri Lankan Pizza Hut restaurants to strategically improve experience activities based on empirically discovered local factors of consumer satisfaction (Widowati & Tsabita, 2017). This study aims to assist restaurant managers and decision-makers in Sri Lanka, including Pizza Hut, in identifying critical aspects of experiential marketing and understanding how they influence customer satisfaction (Amin & Tarun, 2019).

1.2 Literature Review

1.2.1 Experiential Marketing

Experiential marketing refers to the ability of a commodity to transfer psychological encounters to the clients and the capability of the commodity to hold out the consumer's mind through consumption (Fatmawati et al., 2017). By providing people with

memorable, satisfying experiences, experiential marketing engages their thoughts and emotions (Araci et al., 2017).

According to some studies, there are some significant factors in experiential marketing which business firms create intending to pledge encounters to their clients, compromise escapades, surroundings, and vibe (Yuan & Wu, 2008). Thus, to be ahead of the business run and win over the market over others, fabricating and giving unforgettable, idiosyncratic yet feasible encounters for the consumers are essential for businesses (Rageh Ismail et al., 2011).

Experiential marketing enhances customer satisfaction by creating positive experiences, and research shows a strong link between its components and customer satisfaction, which is influenced by sensing, feeling, thinking, acting, and relating (M. Wu & Tseng, 2014). Despite the fact that there is literature on various countries and industries, it is crucial to examine how experiential marketing strategies impact clients in a different market, such as the restaurant industry in Sri Lanka including Pizza Hut, because consumers' perceptions of restaurant attributes and their propensity for loyalty and satisfaction are greatly influenced by where they live and how they interact with brands (Seock & Lin, 2011).

A framework for experiential marketing was developed by Schmitt (1999), who combined traditional marketing concepts with new ideas. The framework, known as Strategic Experiential Modules (SEM), consists of five elements: Sense, Feel, Think, Act, and Relate. SEM model can be better discussed through mentioned five

elements as described below (Schmitt, 2010).

1.2.2 Sense Marketing

According to Maghnati et al. (2012), sense experience refers to the perceptions and impressions customers build about products or services based on their sensory interactions.

Nigam (2012) referred, sense experiences encompass the sensory and tangible elements of a product or encounter, appealing to the five senses: sight, sound, scent, taste, and touch. By incorporating these elements into offering products and services, organisations aim to add a layer of beauty, excitement, and satisfaction. This unique sensory approach helps the organisations stand out in the market and allows them to forge connections with their customers (McCole, 2004).

According to M. Wu & Tseng (2014), sense is a significant predictor of customer satisfaction. On the basis of the discussions above, the following hypothesis has been developed.

H₁: Sense has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction.

1.2.3 Feel Marketing

Feel marketing is positive or negative feelings toward a company product or service that will influence the extent to which it is consumed (Nigam, 2012). Rytel (2010) defined emotional marketing as a substantive shift in marketing management based on the design of emotional ties among the company and the consumer as the key

motivator of customers purchasing decisions.

According to Liyanapathirana & Nishadi (2020), *feel* refers to customers' emotional reactions to a company's brand, often shaped by their experiences at the point of consumption, indicating that friendly service from the sales organisation can significantly enhance customer satisfaction. Thus, the hypothesis below originated.

H₂: *Feel* has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction.

1.2.4 Think Marketing

Think marketing appeals to the intellect, inspiring creativity and motivating consumers to solve problems and create meaningful experiences while promoting harmony and peace (Schmitt, 2010).

The primary purpose of think marketing is to develop consumer intelligence and satisfy the consumer with creativity (Indrawati & Fatharani, 2016). Consumer intelligence hinges on cognitive processes that facilitate creative perception, interaction, and management of experiences, thereby enhancing these cognitive abilities among consumers (LaSalle, 2003).

Furthermore, consumer experiences greatly affect the thinking and cognitive process regarding the brand and products which the brand serves (Gentile et al., 2007). According to Fatmawati et al. (2017), think marketing has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction. Considering the above arguments, the below hypothesis is formulated.

H₃: *Think* has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction.

1.2.5 Act Marketing

Act marketing is acquainted with regard to the design of the experiences on individual's element through the way the consumer action, either clandestinely or in the corporation between each other and with groups of members. The aim is to modify the action and patterns of relating to a long period of time in sponsored of the selective products or services (Nigam, 2012).

However, behaviours and styles of living can be modifications by presenting various kinds of desires, applying inspiration and affection (Gentile et al., 2007). In the words of Sehani & Hettiarachchy (2022) marketers focus on consumers' behaviours and actions to showcase different ways of living and interacting globally. They consider customers' physical traits, lifestyles, and attitudes when creating these experiences, as well as the social interactions that happen with others.

According to Indrawati & Fatharani (2016), Act marketing has a significant impact on customer satisfaction. Thus, the below hypothesis is derived.

H₄: *Act* has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction.

1.2.6 Relate Marketing

Relate marketing aims to connect someone with something outside of themselves (Fatmawati et al., 2017). Consumers can specifically build connections with social entities through buying and using products and services (Maghnati et al., 2012). In their study, Hsin Chang & Wang (2011) emphasise the importance of consumers associating their experiences with social

categories and larger social structures through consumption. This process is not only about obtaining specific goods and services but is also one of the most important ways to gain social acceptance and build social identity (Nigam, 2012).

Relate marketing has a significant impact on customer satisfaction (Indrawati & Fatharani, 2016; M. Wu & Tseng, 2014). However, M. Wu & Tseng (2014) defined relate dimension as the least important element among the elements in the SEM model. Considering the above arguments, the following hypothesis is formulated.

H₅: Relate has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction.

2. METHODOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

2.1 Research Design

This study employs a deductive approach to examine and prove an existing theory. Primary data was obtained via a structured questionnaire. Customers who dined at Pizza Hut restaurants in Sri Lanka were considered the population of the study.

With a 95% confidence level, the sample size of 305 customers was chosen from the target population using the convenience sampling method by the researcher, who based his selection on the judgment of "customers who dined in Pizza Hut restaurants". Considering that Pizza Hut operates over a hundred locations, collecting data from every customer is not feasible. Therefore, a sample size of 305 respondents was selected for convenience and efficiency in data collection. This sample is intended to

provide insights that can be generalised to the broader target population.

Consequently, a self-administered questionnaire was made available to the sample responders online using Google Forms. Customers in this survey were asked to answer on a five-point Likert scale, where one represented "strongly disagree" and five represented "strongly agree." The data analysis was done using the SPSS software suite.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

Building on a comprehensive literature review, the following conceptual framework provides a graphical depiction of the impact of experiential marketing on customer satisfaction. This framework was then subjected to empirical analysis using data that was collected. Therefore, this research aims to investigate the impact of experiential marketing on customer satisfaction.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is developed based on "Experiential Marketing" by Schmitt (1999). The independent variable of the study is experiential marketing, which consists of five sub-variables: Sense, Feel, Think, Act, and Relate. The dependent variable is customer satisfaction.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	125	41%
Female	180	59%

Source: Survey Data (2023)

The majority of the respondents surpassing more than half; females claim 59% while the male respondent percentage is 41%.

Table 2. Age of Respondents

Age	Percentage
Below 25	54.1%
Between 25 – 35	26.6%
Between 36 – 45	9.2%
Between 46 – 55	6.9%
Above 55	3%

Source: Survey Data (2023)

According to Table 2, Most respondents are from the “Below 25” age group, claiming 54.1% of total respondents, while the “Between 25 – 35” age group is following the “Below 25” age group, representing 26.6%. The percentage of the “Between 36 - 45” age group is less than half that of the “Between 25 - 35” age group, claiming 9.2%. Age groups “Between 45 -55” and “Above 55” represent the least number of respondents, 6.9% and 3%, respectively.

Table 3. Regions of Respondents

Province	Percentage
Central	11.8%
Eastern	3.6%
Northwestern	3.9%
Northern	3.0%
Sabaragamuwa	7.5%
Southern	37.0%
Uva	4.3%
Western	28.9%

Source: Survey Data (2023)

Most of the respondents are from the Southern Province, representing 37% of the total respondents, while the Western Province follows the respondents of the Southern Province, which is 28.9%. Western Province is followed by Central Province, Sabaragamuwa Province, Uva Province, Northwestern Province and Eastern Province, with 11.8%, 7.5%, 4.3%, 3.9%, and 3.6% respectively. The lowest number of respondents is from the Northern Province, which accounts for 3%.

3.2 Factor Analysis

Table 4. Factor Analysis

Variable	Items	Factor Loading
Sense	SE1	.821
	SE2	.886
	SE3	.781
Feel	FE1	.775
	FE2	.688

	FE3	.679
	FE4	.807
Think	TH1	.827
	TH2	.797
Act	AC1	.768
	AC2	.803
	AC3	.601
Relate	RE1	.865
	RE2	.868
	RE3	.831
Customer Satisfaction	CS1	.639
	CS2	.689
	CS3	.744
	CS4	.759

Source: Survey Data (2023)

According to factor analysis, all the items have indicated factor loading estimates higher than 0.6.

Table 5. KMO and Barlett's Test of Sphericity

KMO	Barlett's Test of Sphericity
0.883	0.0000

Source: Survey Data (2023)

Sampling adequacy of data used in factor analysis can be determined through KMO and Barlett's test. The KMO value indicated in Table 5 is 0.883, which is greater than 0.5, and the 0.0000 value of Barlett's Test is lower than 0.05, which ultimately means that factor analysis is useful with the data set.

3.3 Convergent Validity

Table 6. Convergent Validity

	AVE	Composite Reliability
Sense	0.690	0.869
Feel	0.547	0.827
Think	0.660	0.795
Act	0.532	0.771
Relate	0.731	0.891
Customer Satisfaction	0.503	0.801

Source: Survey Data (2023)

All average variance extracted (AVE) values are greater than 0.5 and between 0.503 and 0.731, according to "Table 6". Furthermore, CR values exceed 0.7, indicating the established validity of the constructs.

3.4 Discriminant Validity

Table 7. Discriminant Validity

	Sense	Feel	Think	Act	Relate
Sense	.831				
Feel	.553	.740			
Think	.305	.384	.812		
Act	.405	.620	.368	.729	
Relate	.386	.421	.627	.379	.855

Source: Survey Data (2023)

The diagonals in Table 7 display the AVE's square root, while the off diagonals represent the correlations between the constructs. The square root of every AVE is greater than the correlation between any two latent variables. Thus, it is possible to

conclude that the researcher attained discriminant validity to the extent.

3.5 Reliability

Table 8. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Sense	0.865
Feel	0.866
Think	0.864
Act	0.813
Relate	0.946
Customer Satisfaction	0.913

Source: Survey Data (2023)

Figures in Table 8 varying between 0.813 and 0.946 are higher than the threshold level of 0.7 and indicate good reliability.

3.7 Regression Analysis

Table 9. Regression Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.815	.665	.659	.36383

Source: Survey Data (2023)

Customer satisfaction and the independent variables have a medium positive correlation, as indicated by the R-value of 0.815, demonstrating the independent variables' linear solid link with the dependent variable.

The independent variables in the suggested predictive model can account for 65.9% of

the variation in customer satisfaction, according to the Adjusted R squared value of 0.659. Based on the collection of explanatory factors it contains, this indicates that the model explains more than half of the variability observed in satisfaction levels. Considering this, the model's ability to forecast factors influencing customer satisfaction is comparatively strong. However, 34.1% of the variation remains unexplained, suggesting that crucial factors other than those covered by the current variable set affect satisfaction.

Table 10. ANOVA Table

	Regression	Residual	Total
Sum of Square	78.430	39.579	118.009
df	5	299	304
Mean Square	15.686	.132	
F	118.500		
Sig	0.0000		

Source: Survey Data (2023)

The computed p-value is 0.000, indicated in Table 10, which is much less than the significance level of 0.05. This suggests that there is substantial statistical evidence for a strong relationship between the dataset's independent variables and customer satisfaction, and this study's regression model is fit and appropriate.

Table 11. Coefficients Table

	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	.412	.165			2.497	.273
Sense	.077	.038	.084		2.035	.043
Feel	.269	.049	.261		5.461	.000
Think	.064	.035	.079		1.799	.073
Act	.250	.037	.297		6.803	.000
Relate	.274	.037	.336		7.444	.000

Source: Survey Data (2023)

Multiple regression equation can be formed as,

$$\text{Customer Satisfaction (Y)} = 0.412 + 0.077(\text{Sense}) + 0.269(\text{Feel}) + 0.064(\text{Think}) + 0.250(\text{Act}) + 0.274(\text{Relate}) \quad [01]$$

3.8 Hypothesis Testing

H1: Sense has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction.

Table 12 shows that sense has a p-value of 0.043, less than the significance criterion of 0.05. Thus, sense marketing has a significant positive impact on client satisfaction. The β

value is +0.084, indicating a positive relationship between variables. Thus, assuming the first hypothesis (H1), the conclusion can be drawn that sense has a significant positive impact on consumer satisfaction. Supporting the findings of this study, the study done by Liyanapathirana & Nishadi (2020) identified a significant impact on customer satisfaction by sense.

H2: Feel has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction.

The p-value of 0.0000 indicates a significant relationship between feel and customer satisfaction ($p < 0.05$). The β value of feel is +0.261, indicating a positive impact between variables. Thus, it is apparent that feel has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction. Thus, the second hypothesis (H2) can be adopted. This adoption can be further justified through the study done by M. Wu & Tseng (2014).

H3: Think has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction.

The p-value of think is 0.73, which is greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant relationship between think and customer satisfaction. The β value of think (+0.079) indicates a positive correlation between the two variables. However, the third hypothesis cannot be adopted because there is no significant connection between the variables. Therefore, the third hypothesis (H3) has to be rejected. However, in literature, Liyanapathirana & Nishadi (2020) demonstrated that think marketing has a significant impact on customer satisfaction while M. Wu & Tseng (2014) demonstrated that think marketing does not have a significant impact on customer satisfaction.

Table 12. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Variable	β Value	β Value Sign	Sig	Conclusion
H ₁	Sense	0.084	Positive	0.043	Accepted
H ₂	Feel	0.261	Positive	0.0000	Accepted
H ₃	Think	0.079	Positive	0.73	Rejected
H ₄	Act	0.297	Positive	0.000	Accepted
H ₅	Relate	0.336	Positive	0.000	Accepted

Source: Survey Data (2023)

H4: Act has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction.

The beta value of act is +0.297, and a positive influence between variables can be observed. Act revealed a p-value of 0.000, explaining there is a substantial impact between act and customer satisfaction as $p < 0.05$. It is evident from this that the act significantly impacts customer satisfaction. As a result, it is possible to adopt the fourth hypothesis (H4). Concreting the findings of the study, Indrawati & Fatharani (2016) found a significant impact on customer satisfaction by act marketing.

H5: Relate has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction.

Table 12 reveals that the p-value for relate is 0.0000, which is below the significance level of 0.05. As a result, relate marketing has a significant impact on customer satisfaction. Furthermore, the β value of +0.336 suggests a positive association between variables. Thus, accepting the fifth hypothesis (H5), it can be concluded that relate has a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction. This conclusion can be supported by the study of Yeh et al. (2019).

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE IMPLICATIONS

The objective of this study was to examine the impact of experiential marketing on customer satisfaction in the restaurant industry, with a specific focus on Pizza Hut in Sri Lanka. This study contributes to the extant literature by investigating experiential marketing in the restaurant sector of Sri Lanka. The findings of this research corroborate that four out of five dimensions of experiential marketing - sense, feel, act, and relate - positively influence customer satisfaction at Pizza Hut establishments in Sri Lanka. Among these strategic experiential modules, relate marketing emerged as the most influential ($\beta = 0.336$), followed by act ($\beta = 0.297$), feel ($\beta = 0.261$), and sense ($\beta = 0.084$). These results are consistent with previous studies that have emphasised the significance of multisensory and emotional experiences in engendering customer satisfaction (Ellitan, 2022; Indrawati & Fatharani, 2016; Schmitt, 2010).

Notably, the study revealed that the think dimension did not significantly influence customer satisfaction, opposing previous

research that suggested its importance (Brakus et al., 2009). This unexpected outcome emphasises the necessity for further investigation into the role of cognitive engagement in the restaurant sector, particularly in the Sri Lankan market. It challenges assumptions regarding the universality of cognitive engagement in experiential marketing and presents new avenues for theoretical exploration.

This research contributes to the existing literature on experiential marketing in several ways. The study implies the applicability of Schmitt's (2010) Strategic Experiential Modules in Sri Lanka, thus extending the generalizability of this framework. Furthermore, the study offers empirical support for the relative significance of elements of experiential marketing in Pizza Hut, which develops the understanding of the complex interactions between these variables and customer satisfaction.

This study offers valuable insights to restaurant managers and decision-makers, especially global franchises expanding their business to emerging economies like Sri Lanka. Managers need to focus on developing experiences that are multi-sensory, emotional and behavioural. The high value of relate marketing indicates that the approaches promoting social relations and shared experiences of customers might be especially effective. Since the think dimension is insignificant, managers may have to reconsider incorporating the cognitive aspects into their experiential marketing strategies. They may have to look for more suitable contextual solutions. Out of the four elements, relate marketing

showed the most significant impact, yet a combination of all the sense, feel, act and relate elements would be most effective in achieving high levels of customer satisfaction.

This research has several limitations that offer possibilities for future investigations. The narrow scope, focusing on a single restaurant chain, restricts the broad applicability of the findings. Future research could focus on different restaurant categories or other food service establishments to give a broader view of the industry. The cross-sectional research design used in the study also restricts the findings in terms of the temporal dynamics of the experiential marketing effects. Such temporal patterns could be examined in long-term studies and could provide important information. Although this research focused on the experiential marketing dimensions, future research could examine how different contextual factors (like economic environment or level of urbanisation) affect the effectiveness of experiential marketing strategies.

The think dimension has been found to be insignificant, and further research should be conducted into this aspect. Perhaps qualitative studies could shed light on why this is the case and how cognitive aspects can be integrated into the concept of experiential marketing most effectively. Further research could also explore moderating factors such as demographic or psychographic characteristics of the customers on the effects of experiential marketing on customer satisfaction.

Thus, this research provides an understanding of the importance of

implementing experiential marketing concepts in enhancing customer satisfaction in the restaurant industry of developing markets, including Sri Lanka. This paper offers guidelines and suggestions to managers and decision-makers and stresses the importance of future research to improve these strategies in different settings.

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